

Questionnaire

The Effects of the ‘Our Love, Our Control’ Online Programe on Sexual Health Literacy (SHL) and Behaviors in Preventing Unintended Pregnancy and Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs) among Adolescents in Agricultural Areas during Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) Situation in Thailand

1. The questionnaire consisted of four categories with 70 items as follows:
 - 1). Sociodemographic characteristics (10 questions)
 - 2). Attribute and pattern of sexual behaviors (15 questions)
 - 3). Sexual health literacy (30 questions)
 - 4). Behaviors for preventing unintended pregnancy and STDs (15 questions)
2. Please complete every item of the questionnaire as fully as possible. The time needed for questionnaire completion is about 30 minutes.
3. Data collected from this questionnaire will be treated as confidential; in any future presentation, the information will be revealed in summary format only.

Part 1 Sociodemographic characteristics
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No	Question	Answer
1	Sex	()1. Male ()2. Female
2	Grade point average
3	Religion	()1. Buddhist ()2. Christianity ()3. Islam ()4. Other (please indicate).....
4	Average income per dayBaht (per day)
5	Daily sufficient income	()1. Sufficient income and saving ()2. Sufficient income ()3. Insufficient income
6	Parents' marital status	()1. Married ()2. Separated ()3. Divorced ()4. Widowed
7	Co-living with others	()1. Co-living with parents ()2. Co-living with father/ mother ()3. Co-living with friend ()4. Co-living with relative
8	Occupation of parent	()1. Agricultural ()2. Civil servant ()3. Self-employ ()4. Merchant
9	Relationship with the parents during the past year	()1. Very good ()2. Good ()3. Moderate ()4. Poor
10	Primigravid age

Part 2: Sociodemographic characteristics

No	Question	Answer
1	Sexual orientation	()1. Heterosexual ()2. Homosexual ()3. Bisexual
2	Having a boy or girl friend	()1. Yes ()2. No
3	Having temporary partner/s?	()1. Yes ()2. No
4	Hugging experiences	()1. Yes ()2. No
5	Kissing experiences	()1. Yes ()2. No
6	Sexual intercourse experiences	()1. Yes ()2. No
7	Night life	()1. Yes ()2. No
8	Alcoholic history	()1. Yes ()2. No
9	Drug use history	()1. Yes ()2. No
10	Preventive pregnancy and STD history	()1. Coitus interruptus ()2. Fertility Awareness Method ()3. Condom ()4. Emergency contraceptive pill ()5. Contraceptive pill ()6. Contraceptive injection ()7. Contraceptive implant ()8. Have never prevented pregnancy ()9. Other (please indicate).....
11	How often do students/couples use condoms to prevent STIs?	()1. Always ()2. Very often ()3. Sometimes ()4. Never

Part 2: Sociodemographic characteristics (continued)

No	Question	Answer
12	Who is the supplier of drugs/devices to prevent pregnancy or STIs?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Yourself <input type="checkbox"/> 2. A boy or girl friend <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Parents <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Friend <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Superficial acquaintance <input type="checkbox"/> 6. Other (please indicate)
13	Are you think that currently the medication/ equipment for pregnancy prevention is easily accessible?	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Agree <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Disagree <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Not sure
14	Consultation history about preventive pregnancy and STDs	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Girlfriend/Boyfriend <input type="checkbox"/> 2. Friend/Acquaintance <input type="checkbox"/> 3. Parents <input type="checkbox"/> 4. Medical officers <input type="checkbox"/> 5. Teacher <input type="checkbox"/> 6. TV/Radio <input type="checkbox"/> 7. Book/Pamphlet <input type="checkbox"/> 8. Internet <input type="checkbox"/> 9. Other (<i>please indicate</i>).....
15	Consequences of sexual intercourse	<input type="checkbox"/> 1. Yes <input type="checkbox"/> 2. No

Part 3: Sexual Health Literacy

Question	Level				
	Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1. I'm able to <u>find information</u> that I'm concerned about regarding problems with preventing pregnancy / STI's.					
2. I am able to find information about preventing pregnancy / STI's <u>from different sources</u> such as from people who know, from offline and online media as follows.					
3. I'm always <u>open to receiving information</u> about preventing pregnancy/STI's so that my partner and I are not pregnant/ contract STI's while still studying.					
4. I receive news information about preventing pregnancy/STI's by <u>listening to others talk or share stories</u> .					
5. I usually <u>rely on others</u> in finding information about preventing pregnancy/ STI's.					
6. I'm able to <u>search health service provider source</u> that is related to the issue of preventing pregnancy/ STI's.					
7. I'm worried to <u>visit the doctor or health service provider</u> regarding preventing pregnancy/STI's.					
8. I've decided to <u>choose a health service provider source</u> that is exactly as expected which is related to preventing pregnancy/ STI's.					
9. I'm confident that the health service source I choose to use is <u>correctly related with the problem</u> of preventing pregnancy/STI's and meets my expectations.					
10. I searched for <u>health service provider source</u> that prevents pregnancy/STI's that I'm concerned about or that I'm going through.					
11. I believe that I'm able to correctly <u>fill in the information</u> on preventing pregnancy /STI's, the way the agency or the health service facility needs the information filled.					
12. It is difficult for me to <u>follow the manual</u> of pregnancy/STI's prevention correctly as stated in the manual or the medical document.					
13. I'm able to <u>read and understand</u> the information about preventing pregnancy /STI's that other people can write.					

Part 3: Sexual Health Literacy

Question	Level				
	Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
14. Every time I read the information regarding preventing pregnancy /STI's I'm able to <u>read and understand the entire message</u> .					
15. I'm able to listen and understand the content that the health care provider relayed to me about preventing pregnancy /STI's.					
16. I <u>often compare information</u> about preventing pregnancy /STI's before deciding to trust and follow them.					
17. When there is new information about preventing pregnancy /STI's it is <u>very difficult for me to verify the accuracy of the source</u> of information before deciding to believe or follow it.					
18. I often research and compare information about preventing pregnancy /STI's from many sources to confirm proper understanding for myself.					
19. I know where to find information about preventing pregnancy /STI's to confirm the accuracy of the information before believing and following.					
20. I'm worried to ask or consult from people that know or from health service providers about the quality and accuracy of the information or practices to prevent pregnancy/ STI's.					
21. I feel that I have good <u>information</u> about preventing pregnancy/STI's.					
22. I have <u>enough information</u> about preventing pregnancy/STI's to be able to take care of my health.					
23. I'm confident that I have information about preventing pregnancy/STI's, that I'm able to search that can be used to enhance and prevent one's health.					
24. I have information about preventing pregnancy/STI's <u>that is important</u> enough to be used to take care of my health.					
25. I <u>don't have time</u> to do activities for myself to prevent pregnancy/STI's.					
26. I've made plans to do activities to prevent pregnancy/STI's that are important for my good health.					

Part 3: Sexual Health Literacy (continued)

Question	Level				
	Strongly agree	Agree	Not sure	Disagree	Strongly disagree
27. Since I'm on duty I'm not able to spare my time to prevent pregnancy/STI's.					
28. <u>It's very difficult</u> to prevent pregnancy/STI's as I intend.					
29. I often <u>direct myself</u> to regularly prevent pregnancy/STI's to be in good health.					
30. I've made <u>adjustments to the surrounding environment</u> so that I can practice preventing pregnancy/STI's					

Part 4 Behaviors in Preventing Unintended Pregnancy and Sexually Transmitted Diseases (STDs)

Question	Level				
	Always	Very often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
1. If my friend invites me to an entertainment venue I must go along.					
2. If an opposite sex friend invites me to an entertainment venue to go just the two of us then I will deny.					
3. I open porn that is related to sexual intercourse.					
4. I read books magazine /cartoons that act sexually seductive.					
5. My opposite sex friend and I avoid watching videos that have sex-related content.					
6. When I feel the need to have sex I will help myself by masturbating.					
7. I go to watch movies, listen to music or go out with a guy friend alone.					
8. I allow my male friend to hold hands as a way to express love for each other.					
9. I go to entertainment venues to gain life experience.					
10. I'm with a friend of the opposite sex at a place with romantic ambience.					
11. I will dress up appropriately when I'm with a friend of the opposite sex.					
12. I avoid living alone with a friend of the opposite sex.					
13. I have ways to prevent pregnancy/STI 's that are beneficial for all.					
14. When I'm frustrated or upset with my family I will run away from home.					
15. I ask for advice from my parents when there is a problem with sexual health or adjusting with sex or having a male friend.					